

Weed Control and Growth Regulation

Control of Weedy Rice with Spot Treatment of Clethodim and Glufosinate

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Spot-spraying is an herbicide application method that conducts directed sprays using a precise handheld or backpack sprayer with an adjustable nozzle. Spot spraying is especially useful for the control of herbicide-resistant weeds, and it greatly reduces the use of chemicals. On the other hand, chemical control of weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* f. *spontanea* Roshev.) is difficult due to the same species of cultivated rice. Spot spraying can be a logical approach for the weedy rice challenge. In preliminary studies in the greenhouse, the doses of clethodim and glufosinate, which controlled weedy rice by 90%, were determined as 80 g ai ha⁻¹ and 420 g ai ha⁻¹, respectively. In this study, spot spray experiment was carried out at different herbicide doses and at different application times in field conditions. The aim of this study is to evaluate the efficacy of clethodim and glufosinate spot spraying applications in the rice field.

The experiment was conducted on randomized block design with 5 replications at the Rice Experiment Station, Biggs, CA, in 2022. M209 rice variety was cultivated in the field, the trial was carried out in two locations (North and South Fields). Clethodim and glufosinate were used to control weedy rice in field. Clethodim rate was 0.08% v/v (1×=150 g ai ha⁻¹) and 0.16% v/v (2×=300 g ai ha⁻¹). Glufosinate rate was 0.26% v/v (1×=492 g ai ha⁻¹) and 0.52% (2×=984 g ai ha⁻¹). Clethodim was applied at rice 3-4 leaf seedling stage (BBCH13) and tillering stage (BBCH23), however, glufosinate was applied only at the panicle emergence stage (BBCH52). Backpack sprayer application pressure was set to 75 PSI and application area was 100×50 cm. Herbicide spray volume was 187 L ha⁻¹ of water. Observations were taken at application point (100×50cm application area), first dispersion area (beyond application point at 0-25 cm), and second dispersion area (beyond the application point 25-50 cm) to determine how far clethodim and glufosinate would spread, and to determine rice injury within those distances.

The north field at 1× clethodim had 97% and 73% efficacies when applied at the 3-4 leaf stage and tillering stage, respectively. No injury was detected in the first and second dispersion areas for 1× application. The 2× application rate of clethodim gave 83% rice injury in the treated area. In terms of dispersion, the injury was 7% in the first dispersion area, but no injuries were seen second dispersion area in 2× clethodim. Glufosinate gave 100% rice control at panicle emergence stage. Plant injury was 5% and 10% in the first dispersion area, however, no injuries were observed in the second dispersion area for 1× and 2× glufosinate rates, respectively.

In the south field, 1× clethodim rate provided 93% and 89% rice injury when applied at the 3-4 leaf stage and tillering stage, respectively. No injury was detected in the first and second dispersion areas. The 2× application rate of clethodim gave 93% rice injury. In terms of dispersion, the injury was 8% in the first dispersion area, but no injuries were seen second dispersion area. All rates of glufosinate gave 100% rice injury when applied at panicle emergence stage. Plant injury was 5% and 10% in the first dispersion area, but no injuries were reported in the second dispersion area for 1× and 2× glufosinate rates, respectively.

In summary, clethodim and glufosinate were successful to control weedy when applied as a spot treatment. The efficacy of herbicides was between 73 to 100% depending on the application time and application dose. Glufosinate was more effective than clethodim. The efficacy of clethodim was decreased when application time was delayed. One of the most important results is that both herbicides had little adverse dispersion effects. Even at high spray doses, the dispersion extended up to 15 cm beyond the application point and the plant injury was observed up to 10% in the first dispersion area. This result indicated that clethodim and glufosinate have great potential as spot spray treatments for the management of weedy rice.

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